

Targeting and activation of monocytes by liposomes with TLR7 agonists

Daniel Zucker^{1,*}, Simon Skjøde Jensen², Houman Pourhassan², Jeanette E. Wern², Roberto Maj³, Alcide Barberis³, and Thomas Lars Andresen¹

¹Department of Micro- and Nanotechnology, Center for Nanomedicine and Theranostics, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby 2800, Denmark.

²Immune cell Targeting, Bioneer, Hoersholm 2970, Denmark.

³Telormedix SA, Bioggio 6934, Switzerland.

*To whom the correspondence should be addressed., e-mail: zucker@posteo.de

Supplementary Information

Materials and Methods

Materials

SP buffer was prepared by dissolving 290 mM sucrose and 10 mM sodium phosphate in MQ water.

The pH was adjusted to 7.4 by addition of NaOH. PD-10 columns were packed with 13 ml of DEAE Sepharose CL-6B with 25% of SP buffer.

The lysolipids 1-oleoyl-2-hydroxy-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (Lyso-C18-PC), 1-palmitoyl-2-hydroxy-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (Lyso-C16-PC), and 1-Lauroyl-2-hydroxy-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (Lyso-C12-PC) were purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids (Alabaster, Alabama).

Physical characterization of free TMXs in water

TMX powders were dissolved in DMSO to a final concentration of 20 mM. Two different methods were investigated for preparation of nanoparticles of TMX: fast dilution (TMX solution was diluted

by addition of water) and slow injection (TMX solution was slowly injected into water by a syringe with a 25G needle). In all preparations the final concentrations of DMSO and TMX were 5% and 0.5 mM, respectively. The size and ζ -potential were measured by dynamic light scattering (DLS) using ZetaPALS (Brookhaven, SE). In order to achieve a count rate of 200-500 kcps during DLS measurement further dilutions by water were applied to some preparations.

Separation between liposomes and free TMXs

TMX-201 was dissolved at concentration of 2.4 g/l in SP buffer with 14% DMSO. TMX-202 was dissolved at concentration of 1.2 g/l in SP buffer with 24% DMSO. 500 μ l of these solutions were uploaded on the columns.

Liposomes composed of POPC:DOTAP:TMX:Rhod-DOPE 71.75:14:4:0.25 were prepared by ethanol injection method. Liposomal TMX-201 (lipid 7.6 mM, TMX-201 439 μ g/ml) and Liposomal TMX-202 (lipid 7.3 mM, TMX-201 380 μ g/ml) were prepared in SP buffer. 850 μ l of these solutions were uploaded on the columns.

The columns were washed with SP buffer, NaCl 1.4 M, NaCl 1.1 M and Ethanol (EtOH) 20%, and finally with NaCl 0.7 M and Ethanol 50%. Fractions of 2 ml were collected, and their optical absorbances at 278 nm and 570 nm were measured. These absorbances are proportional to the TMX and Rhodamine concentrations, respectively. Since neither lipid nor TMX were detected in the fractions that were eluted with NaCl 1.4 M, these elution profiles are not shown in Fig. S1.

Detection of lipids by thin layer chromatography (TLC)

The TLC was performed as previously described (Protocol 3, in Liposomes - practical approach by Vladimir P. Torchilin, 2nd edition, Oxford University Press, pages 37-39). Lipid stocks of: DOTAP, POPC, Lyso-C18-PC, Lyso-C16-PC, TMX-201, TMX-202, and cholesterol were dissolved in chloroform:methanol 9:1 at concentration of 20 g/l. The liposomal lipids were extracted by Bligh

and Dryer method before doing TLC: The liposomes (POPC:DOTAP:TMX:DOPE-Rhod 80.75:14:5:0.25) were mixed with methanol and chloroform (0.8:1:2 v/v/v) until a clear solution is obtained. Then, 1 ml of 0.1 M HCl were added, and vortexing was applied again. The mixture was centrifuged at 4500 g for 15 min at 4 °C to obtain two clear phases. The lower phase was transferred to a new glass tube.

The following TLC plate was used: Silica gel 60 F₂₅₄, (Product number 1.05554.0001, Merck KGaA, Germany). A mobile phase of chloroform:methanol:water (65:25:4 v/v/v.) was used in order to separate the lipids. The spots of the TMXs could be clearly seen by a UV lamp. Finally, the plates were immersed in a solution of 10% copper⁺² sulfate and 10% phosphoric acid, and then charred with a heat gun at 110 °C until black spots appeared.

Uptake of liposomes by immune cells in whole human blood

In order to calculate the targeting specificity to monocytes, the following assumptions were made: in each liter of blood there are 1.75, 0.83, 0.30, 0.38, and 4.25 billion of T-lymphocytes, natural killer, B-lymphocytes, monocytes, and Neutrophils, respectively. These numbers were taken from Murphy, K. (2007). Immunological constants. Janeway's Immunobiology, New York, Garland Science: page 804.

Supplementary Fig. S1. Elution profiles of liposomes and TMXs from Sepharose DEAE CL-6B columns. A. Liposomes with TMX-201 were uploaded on to the column and the lipid elution was monitored. B. Liposomes with TMX-202 were uploaded on to the column and the lipid elution was monitored. C. Liposomes with TMX-201 were uploaded on to the column and TMX-201 elution was monitored. D. Liposomes with TMX-201 were uploaded on to the column and TMX-202 elution was monitored. E. Free TMX-201 was uploaded on the column and its elution was monitored. F. Free TMX-202 was uploaded on the column and its elution was monitored. Legend: Black circles – elution with SP buffer, red triangles – elution with NaCl 1.1 M and ethanol 20%, blue pluses elution with NaCl 0.7 M and ethanol 50%. RU = relative units.

Supplementary Fig. S2. UV spectrum of TMXs (0.6 mg/ml) in THF in 1 cm quartz cuvettes. The box describes the exact wavelengths and absorptions of the peaks. The aromatic purine group of TMX-201 and TMX-202 is responsible for the UV absorption.

Supplementary Fig. S3. Pictures of the various liposomal formulations after 6 days of storage at 4 °C. These liposomes were purified by SEC and stored in PBS. The lipid compositions of the liposomes were: A) POPC:DOTAP 90:10 B) POPC:DOTAP:TMX-201 88:10:2 C) POPC:DOTAP:TMX-201 88:10:4 D) POPC:DOTAP:TMX-201 81:9:10 E) POPC:DOTAP:TMX-201 72:8:20 F) POPC:DOTAP:TMX-202 88:10:2 G) POPC:DOTAP:TMX-201 88:10:4. A precipitate (ellipse) can be seen in the formulations that contained $\geq 4\%$ of TMXs.

Supplementary Fig. S4. Diameters of liposomes with TMX-201 and TMX-202 during 80 days storage at 4 °C. The lipid composition of the liposomes is POPC:DOTAP:TMX 81:14:5.

Supplementary Fig. S5. Zeta potentials of liposomes with TMX-201 and TMX-202 during 80 days storage at 4 °C. The lipid composition of the liposomes is POPC:DOTAP:TMX 81:14:5.

Supplementary Fig. S6. TLC analysis of storage stability of liposomal formulations. A) Control plate showing the retention distances of the pure lipids: TMX-202, DOTAP, POPC, and lyso phospholipids. The spots are smeared because a little bit too much material was uploaded on the silica. B) Plate of liposomal TMX-201, liposomal TMX-202 and a mixture of POPC:DOTAP:Lyso-C18-PC 55:15:30, showing lack of chemical hydrolysis of liposome lipid components after 4 months storage. The names of the different lipids are shown in red near the relevant spots. The blue text in panel B describes that type of the formulation that was uploaded onto each lane. Due to the sensitivity of this method, we conclude that the degradation of the lipids was below 14 %.

Supplementary Fig. S7. Positive ion MALDI-TOF mass spectrums of single lipids. The exact molecular weights of each lipid are mentioned in the titles. The m/z ratios of the main peaks are labelled on the histograms. A) POPC has two main adducts: POPC + H^+ - 760.2, and POPC + K^+ - 798.2. B) DOTAP has two main adducts: DOTAP $^+$ - 662.2 and (Z)-2-(decanoyloxy)-N,N,N-trimethyl-3-(oleoyloxy)propan-1-aminium $^+$ - 552.2. C) DDA has one main peak DDA $^+$ - 550.6. D) Lyso-C18-PC has 2 main adducts: Lyso-C18-PC + H^+ - 524.2 and Lyso-C18-PC + K^+ - 562.3. E) Lyso-C16-PC has 3 main adducts: Lyso-C16-PC + H^+ - 496.2, Lyso-C16-PC + K^+ - 534.2, and dimer $^+$ - 991.2. F) Lyso-C12-PC has five main adducts: Lyso-C12-PC + H^+ - 440.3, Lyso-C12-PC + K^+ - 478.2, dimer $^+$ - 879.1, and dimer + K^+ - 917.1. G) TMX-201 has two main adducts: TMX-201 + 2 K^+ - 1160.8 and TMX-201 + K^+ - 1122.9. H) TMX-202 has two main adducts: TMX-202 + 2 K^+ - 958.9 and TMX-202 + K^+ - 996.8.

A) DOTAP:POPC mole ratio 15:85 Mw 662.6:759.6

B) DOTAP:Lyso-C18:POPC mole ratio 15:10:75 Mw 662.6:523.4:759.6

C) DOTAP:Lyso-C18:POPC mole ratio 15:30:55 Mw 662.6:523.4:759.6

Supplementary Fig. S8. Positive ion MALDI-TOF mass spectrums of mixtures lipids , which were extracted from liposomes by Bligh and Dyer extraction. The exact molecular weights (Mw) of the lipids are mentioned in the title of each panel. **A)** Liposomes composed of DOTAP:POPC at mole ratios of 15:85. **B)** Liposomes composed of DOTAP:Lyso-C18-PC:POPC at mole ratios of 15:10:85. **C)** Liposomes composed of DOTAP:Lyso-C18-PC:POPC at mole ratios of 15:30:85. A substantial increase in the peaks of Lyso-C18-PC (524 and 562 m/z) can be seen when the mole ratio of it was elevated.

Supplementary Fig. S9. Effect of liposomes size on in vitro targeting to human monocytes. The zeta potentials of the liposomes were ~38 mV, and the lipid composition POPC:Chol:DDA:TMX-202 52:30:13:5 for the 200 and 400 nm, while 53:30:12:5 for the 100 nm liposomes.

Supplementary Fig. S10. Effect of liposomes size on in vitro targeting and activation of human monocytes. In treatments with TMX-202 the drug concentration was 1 µM. The zeta potentials of the liposomes were ~38 mV. The lipid composition of the liposomal TMX-202 formulations were POPC:Chol:DDA:TMX-202 52:30:13:5 for the 400 and 200 nm, while 53:30:12:5 for the 100 nm liposomes. For the empty liposomes the lipid compositions were POPC:Chol:DDA 64:30:6 for the 400 nm, POPC:Chol:DDA 62:30:8 for the 200 nm, and POPC:Chol:DDA 61:30:9 for the 100 nm.

Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Size, polydispersity and zeta potential of TMXs aggregates in water

Composition	Preparation method	Diameter (nm)	Polydispersity	Zeta Potential (mV)
TMX-201	slow injection	210±2	0.315	-84.8±0.9
TMX-202	slow injection	748±33	0.347	-63.3±0.8
TMX-201	fast dilution	300±6	0.296	-62.9±1.8
TMX-202	fast dilution	705±28	0.339	-72.2±0.6